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Abbreviations

CCSD(T)	Coupled Cluster with Single, Double and perturbative Triple excitations
CoE	Center of Excellence
DFT	Density Functional Theory
DMC	Diffusion Monte Carlo
EU	European Union
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
HPC	High Performance Computing
KRR	Kernel Ridge Regression
MD	Molecular Dynamics
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Machine Learning Potential
QMC	Quantum Monte Carlo
TREX	Targeting Real chemical accuracy at the EXascale
PIOD	Path-Integral Ornstein–Uhlenbeck Dynamics
SOAP	Smooth Overlap of Atomic Positions
UFP	Ultra-Fast Potential
VMC	Variational Monte Carlo
WP	Work Package

Consortium partners

See grant agreement for a complete list of consortium partners.

CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, France
LIST	Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology, Luxembourg
SISSA	Scuola Internazionale Superiore di Studi Avanzati, Italy
UKON	University of Konstanz, Germany
UT	University of Twente, Netherlands

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Executive summary

The Targeting Real chemical accuracy at the EXascale (TREX) EU Centre of Excellence investigates implementations of Quantum Monte Carlo (QMC) calculations optimized for exascale High Performance Computing (HPC). These calculations are high-accuracy quantum-chemical and materials simulations that are inherently parallelizable and computationally demanding. Thus, they are uniquely suited to utilize and explore the upcoming exascale supercomputer architectures. TREX focuses on the development and promotion of an open-source high-performance software platform of inter-operable flagship codes and exascale-ready libraries.

This scope includes the development, validation, and application of MLPs trained on QMC data generated by TREX codes. These MLPs are fast surrogate models for QMC calculations, enabling acceleration of QMC-based simulations by multiple orders of magnitude. This Periodic Activity Report D4.4 centers on the developed MLPs.

The usual strategy of training an MLP directly on QMC reference data is problematic as it is computationally very expensive to generate sufficient QMC training data. Instead, the group at SISSA developed an MLP that learns the difference between QMC and the lower Density Functional Theory (DFT) level, a so-called Δ -learning approach that requires less QMC training data. This model enabled them to run near-QMC accuracy simulations at the lower cost of DFT calculations.

Based on this, work at UKON and LIST replaced the DFT baseline with another MLP. Modeling the liquid-liquid phase transition of hydrogen under pressure at the DFT level with an MLP proved challenging, however. This line of research is currently pursued further in collaboration with CNRS. The phase transition data was also used to set up a challenging benchmark for MLPs, providing physically motivated performance measures obtained from running accelerated simulations in a fully automated fashion. For this benchmark, many state-of-the-art MLPs fail to reproduce the DFT observables despite low test set errors in energies and forces.

Work at CNRS develops QMC-based MLPs to study proton hydration in large water clusters and the bulk limit. Based on work in TREX [2] they use the FCHL19 [3, 4] representation and an operator kernel regression [4] approach for force learning. For the small water hexamer cluster, MLP results agree with pure QMC results. They are currently studying the impact of QMC noise on the MLP quality and the possibility of including long-range interactions.

The UT group has benchmarked QMC forces to improve the training data accuracy for MLPs. They find that the Variational-Drift-Diffusion approximation yields excellent results for ethanol at room temperature as a prototypical system, requiring only a single determinant. These forces were used to train symmetrized gradient domain (sGD) MLPs, which performed very well compared to sGD MLPs trained on DFT and gold standard coupled-cluster forces. In particular, minimum-energy configurations and barrier heights were correctly estimated.

To better exploit exascale computing facilities for QMC simulations, another group at CNRS has developed a prototype software that uses Machine Learning (ML) to approximate the Jastrow factor, a crucial component in such simulations. The Jastrow factor accounts for electron correlation effects beyond the mean-field approximation. Instead of manually parametrising it, they represent it as a neural network. This approach can capture complex, high-dimensional correlations between electrons and can be efficiently trained and executed on Graphical Processing Units (GPUs), leading to more accurate and efficient QMC simulations.

1 Introduction

TREX is a European Union (EU) Center of Excellence (CoE) in the field of high-accuracy quantum-chemical and materials simulations. The CoE focuses on QMC approaches for solving the quantum many-body problem at the heart of atomistic physics, chemistry and materials science. Due to their inherent parallelizability and high computational cost, QMC approaches, and thus TREX, are uniquely positioned to fully exploit the massive parallelism of the upcoming exascale supercomputer architectures. TREX thus focuses on implementations of QMC approaches optimized for exascale HPC. Specifically, this includes the development and promotion of an open-source, high-performance software platform of interoperable flagship codes and exascale-ready libraries for QMC calculations.

This scope includes the development, validation, and application of ML methods to accelerate QMC calculations in Work Package (WP) 4. This was done primarily by constructing MLPs, which are data-driven surrogate models of QMC potential energy surfaces. Trained on a set of reference QMC calculations for a specific atomistic system, an MLP accurately approximates that systems' potential energy surface at a fraction of the computational cost of QMC calculations. The resulting acceleration by multiple orders of magnitude greatly extends the reach of QMC approaches, enabling running more and longer simulations with larger unit cells, a task that will remain computationally unfeasible using QMC calculations alone for the foreseeable future. Other ways to integrate ML approaches with QMC calculations were explored as well, e.g., learning the Jastrow factor.

Enabling rapid yet accurate predictions of the structure and properties of diverse chemical systems and materials has been a long-standing goal of the atomistic simulation community. Over the last decades, ML has emerged as a powerful tool to tackle this problem. After concluding our projects, we will provide our MLPs to the community. Furthermore, we intend to maintain and further develop the corresponding software. This also includes contributions to and further development of existing MLPs used within TREX, such as the Ultra-Fast Potentials (UFPs) [5] used in the development of QMC Δ -learning MLPs at UKON and LIST. The integration of such MLPs developed by TREX will enable others, e.g., from the MaX CoE, to extend the range or reach of their methodologies by estimating, based on our nearly-exact data, the corrections needed to reach QMC accuracy, or by using these models to identify challenging systems which require QMC treatment.

This Periodic Activity Report D4.4 “Report on release of transferable QMC-quality ML models” centers on the MLPs developed by TREX. It is based on task T4.3 on “workflows to machine-learn QMC accuracy” of work package 4, which includes the development, validation, and application of MLPs trained on QMC reference data generated by TREX codes. This report is also related to the deliverables D4.1 (Report on workflow implementation also in an ensemble mode), D5.2 (Report on ML results delivered for water systems.), and D5.4 (Datasets made available for benchmarking and ML modelling).

2 QMC-DFT Δ -learning models

Due to the high computational cost of QMC calculations, the usual strategy of training an MLP directly on QMC reference data fails as it is too expensive to generate enough QMC training data. Instead, QMC corrections to a computationally cheaper physical baseline method, such as DFT, are employed. This approach is called Δ -learning [6] and has the advantage that learning the correction is an easier learning problem, and thus requires less QMC training data.

The SISSA group developed such a Δ -learning MLP that provides the accuracy of QMC calculations at the cost of DFT calculations. Specifically, they used kernel least-squares regression with Smooth Overlap of Atomic Positions (SOAP) features to learn the difference between DFT with the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) functional and QMC, as well as sparsification via farthest-point sampling. [7] The effect of sparsification is shown in Figure 1. Together, this enabled them to train an accurate model using only 684 QMC calculations of 128-atom configurations of H as reference in total.

They applied this model to study **hydrogen under pressure**, in particular a liquid-liquid phase transition [7] and the principal Deuterium Hugoniot [8]. Through this, they showed how QMC can be successfully combined with Δ -learning to deploy reliable MLPs for complex extended systems across different thermodynamic conditions, keeping the QMC precision at the computational cost of a mean-field calculation.

Figure 1: Learning rate of Δ -learning MLP for hydrogen. Shown are the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) of predicted forces as a function of the number of training local atom environments for liquid hydrogen. From this, the learning rate is estimated, both with sparsification (right panel) and without (left panel). With sparsification, the model error approaches the error of the full model, but using one order of magnitude fewer training data.

3 Towards fully machine-learned models for QMC data

Based on the work in Section 2, the UKON/LIST group worked on replacing the DFT baseline with a ML surrogate model. The resulting MLP would have been fully machine-learned, accelerating simulations of warm dense hydrogen by another few orders of magnitude. However, it turned out that learning the DFT baseline for this system is much harder than learning the smoother difference between DFT and QMC. In retrospect, the discussion between Cheng et al. and Karasiev et al. in Nature [9, 10, 11] can be seen as having hinted at the difficulty of pure MLPs for warm dense hydrogen. This line of research is still being pursued further in collaboration with the CNRS/Paris group, see Section 4.

Turning the challenges in modeling warm dense hydrogen with MLPs into an opportunity, the UKON/LIST group has used the liquid-liquid phase transition in warm dense hydrogen described at the DFT level to set up a challenging **benchmark for MLPs**. The performance of MLPs is commonly measured as the prediction error in energies and forces on data not used for training. While low prediction errors on a test set are necessary, they are not sufficient for good performance in atomistic dynamics simulations. The latter requires physically motivated performance measures obtained from running accelerated simulations. The adoption of such measures, however, has been limited by the effort and domain knowledge required to calculate and interpret them.

To overcome this limitation, data and scripts to automatically quantify the performance of MLPs in dynamics simulations of the liquid-liquid phase transition of hydrogen under pressure were created. Specifically, geometries, energies, forces, and stresses, calculated at the DFT level of theory for different temperatures and mass densities are provided, as well as scripts to automatically calculate, quantitatively compare, and visualize radial distribution functions, as well as stable molecular fractions (Figure 2), pressure, and diffusion coefficients as functions of cell density. For this benchmark, many state-of-the-art MLPs fail to reproduce the liquid-liquid phase transition despite low test set errors in energies and forces. Data and code from this project will be made fully available upon publication. See also Report D5.4 on “Datasets made available for benchmarking and ML modelling.”

4 Towards machine-learning QMC proton hydration

The CNRS/Paris group develops QMC-based MLPs to extend previous QMC results for small water clusters towards the limit of bulk water.

In a recent TREX publication [2], they studied the **protonated water hexamer** (Figure 3), where they unveiled the temperature dependence of the hydrated proton and its dynamics, including proton transfer. In this system, they discovered a remarkably small thermal expansion of the cluster core, and of an optimal temperature range for the proton transfer in the 250–300 K temperature window. For this, they used a combination of variational QMC to compute the electronic wave function and ionic forces on the fly, with a Path-Integral Ornstein–Uhlenbeck Dynamics (PIOUD) [12] simulation to sample the quantum thermal distribution function of the nuclei. The simulations were performed with the **TREX code** TurboRVB. The coupling of QMC with PIOUD is computationally very expensive, and was only possible due to the small size of the system.

Figure 2: *Stable molecular fraction as a function of density* in warm dense hydrogen. Shown are DFT reference fractions (left), ultra-fast potentials with 3-body terms (middle), and MACE message-passing neural network [1] (right). The stable molecular fraction measures the fraction of hydrogen atoms that stay within a given distance of each other for a given number of consecutive simulation steps. Most MLPs in the benchmark were not able to reproduce observables such as the stable molecular fraction.

Thus, to extend these findings to larger clusters and to study proton hydration in the limit of bulk water, they developed an **MLP for water clusters** that combines the accuracy of QMC calculations with the computational efficiency of ML, using the trajectories generated during the above study for training. Their MLP used the FCHL19 [3, 4] representation and Kernel Ridge Regression (KRR). FCHL19 is a computationally efficient and suitable representation for operator kernel regression used here for force learning. Their approach uses “operator quantum machine learning” [4]. The results, based on the trajectories generated during the protonated water hexamer study, are satisfactory: The Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations run using the MLP are stable and produce pair distribution functions in reasonable agreement with the original QMC-driven MD.

They currently study the impact of QMC noise on MLP quality and including long-range interactions to correctly describe charged impurities or defects such as the hydrated proton.

5 QMC force evaluation

In on-going work, the UT group has benchmarked the quality of **QMC forces** for different algorithms and wave functions. In particular, the accuracy of Variational Monte Carlo (VMC) forces was compared to two approximations of the forces in Diffusion Monte Carlo (DMC). One used the local VMC force estimator in DMC. The other one, the so-called Variational-Drift-Diffusion (VDD), is a more advanced approximation that partially accounts for the derivative of the fixed-node wave function. The VD force estimator was found to yield excellent results for the prototypical system under study, ethanol at room temperature, with just one determinant in the Jastrow-Slater wave function. This is in contrast to both VMC and the simpler approximation in DMC which need multiple determinants to obtain the same accuracy. To benchmark the quality of the forces for these three methods, inter-atomic forces were calculated over a large number of configurations of ethanol.

Figure 3: Radial distribution functions in dynamics simulations of the protonated water hexamer. OH^+ is the distance between the central proton and the neighboring oxygen atoms, while O_1O_2 is the distance between the two inner water molecules bridged by the central proton. The vertical lines in the bottom panels show the equilibrium $d_{\text{O}_1\text{O}_2}$ distance at zero temperature.

The use of forces, being the negative gradient of the energy of the simulated system, greatly increases the information available to corresponding MLPs (as opposed to ML models trained on energies alone). Consequently, the **accuracy** of such MLPs is greater for fewer training configurations than that of MLPs trained on energies alone. Machine-learning potentials in combination with the symmetrized gradient domain MLP (sGDML) [13] were trained on the VMC forces as well as on the two approximations of the force estimators in DMC. These MLPs were compared to MLPs trained on deterministic methods such as DFT/PBE-TS and the gold standard in quantum chemistry, Coupled Cluster with Single, Double and perturbative Triple excitations (CCSD(T)). Compared to these deterministic methods, the VMC and VD DMC models perform very well. This is due to the fact that several DFT functionals struggle to correctly estimate the location of the global minimum and of barrier heights. The models trained on VMC and VD DMC reference data, however, did have the correct global minimum and also displayed excellent agreement on the potential barriers compared to CCSD(T). Further tests are currently in progress to assess the quality of the derived MLPs in predicting other physical observables, such as vibrational spectra.

6 Learning the Jastrow factor

The CNRS/Toulouse group are investigating the use of ML to improve the **Jastrow factor**, a crucial component in QMC simulations that accounts for electron correlation effects beyond the mean-field approximation. Traditionally, the Jastrow factor is a manually parameterized function, whose optimization requires significant computational effort. To enhance efficiency and scalability, they propose to represent it as a neural network.

In QMC, one needs an initial N -electron wave function $\Psi_0(\mathbf{R}) = \sum_i c_i D_i(\mathbf{R})$ from a preliminary calculation, where D_i are Slater determinants, and $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{R}^{3N}$ are the Cartesian coordinates of the electrons. The coordinates of the nuclei are fixed. Ψ_0 is improved with a Jastrow factor $\exp(J)$ to take into account electron correlation, and to overcome the basis set limit imposed by the molecular orbitals: $\Psi(\mathbf{R}) = \Psi_0(\mathbf{R}) \times \exp(J(\mathbf{R}))$.

There are many different forms of Jastrow factors, and the optimization of the parameters is usually done by minimizing the energy in a VMC framework. One can then run a DMC calculation using Ψ as a trial wave function, where the only approximation remaining is the fixed-node approximation. The DMC energy is computed as $E_{\text{DMC}} = \langle \Phi | H | \Psi \rangle / \langle \Phi | \Psi \rangle$, where $\Phi(\Psi, \mathbf{R})$ is the fixed-node DMC wave function:

$$\Phi(\Psi, \mathbf{R}) = \Psi(\mathbf{R}) \exp\left(-\int_0^t E_L(\Psi, \mathbf{R}(t)) dt\right) = \Psi(\mathbf{R}) w(\Psi, \mathbf{R}).$$

Here, $\mathbf{R}(t)$ is the coordinate vector of the electrons at time t obtained along a Brownian trajectory, and E_L is the local energy. An analytical expression of Φ is not available, but the DMC algorithm allows sampling it. In VMC, Ψ_0 is multiplied by a Jastrow factor $\exp(J)$. If one conducts a DMC simulation using Ψ_0 as a trial wave function, one samples the density originating from $\Psi_0(\mathbf{R})$ multiplied by a weight function $w(\mathbf{R})$. In both cases, the function by which Ψ_0 is multiplied is a positive function over \mathbb{R}^{3N} , and the nodes of the wave function are imposed by Ψ_0 . As DMC is the exact solution with the constraint that the nodes are kept fixed, the best possible Jastrow factor one can build is

$$\exp(J(\mathbf{R})) = \exp\left(-\int_0^t E_L(\Psi, \mathbf{R}(t)) dt\right).$$

The CNRS/Toulouse group proposes to use ML to find an approximation of the best possible Jastrow factor by fitting the weights used in the branching step of the DMC algorithm as follows: Propose a complex parametrization of the Jastrow factor, such as a neural network, and prepare an initial trial wave function Ψ . Then, run a DMC calculation using Ψ as trial wave function. During the simulation, \mathbf{R} and the associated weight are known at each step, allowing the neural network to learn the weight function. They then modify the trial wave function from Ψ to $\Psi \times \exp(J)$, where $\exp(J)$ is the ML Jastrow factor.

For initial validation, three steps of the above algorithm have been carried out for the hydrogen atom. At each step, a new neural network is trained based on the sampled weight functions using the best wavefunction from the previous steps. The plot of the local energy as a function of electron-nuclear distance is shown in Figure 4. From one iteration to the next, the energy becomes closer to being constant, which is the expected behavior. Further work includes finding a suitable representation of the electron and nuclear coordinates which are given as input to the neural network.

Figure 4: Energy of systematically improved wavefunctions using a product of neural network-based Jastrow functions. The exact energy is shown by a horizontal line at -0.5 which is constant with respect to x . The wavefunction obtained at step three is represented by the red curve.

7 Summary and conclusions

Based on the open-source high-performance exascale-ready inter-operable flagship QMC codes and libraries developed by the TREX consortium, ML models to accelerate QMC calculations were investigated: Δ -learning MLPs by the SISSA group achieved near-QMC accuracy at DFT/PBE cost for warm dense hydrogen. The groups at UKON/LIST and CNRS/Paris explore this further to develop fully ML-based potentials, without the DFT cost. A liquid-liquid phase transition of warm dense hydrogen, modeled at the DFT level, was used to create a benchmark for MLPs at LIST/UKON. Work at CNRS/Paris uses MLPs to study proton hydration in water clusters, extending QMC results. The UT group demonstrated accurate force calculations with VMC and DMC, leading to efficient MLPs. The CNRS/Toulouse group proposed and tested a neural network-based Jastrow factor to improve efficiency and scalability of QMC calculations.

Overall, the work carried out demonstrates that ML, and in particular MLPs, can accelerate QMC calculations by several orders of magnitude. This potentially enables study of systems otherwise not accessible to QMC, e.g., exploration of the phase diagram of warm dense hydrogen and proton hydration in large water clusters via MD simulations. Many challenges remain, including the treatment of long-ranged interactions and the exploitation of error bars provided by QMC.

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